

New Dimensions of Heavy Ion Nuclear Research^ψ

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The applications of nuclear track detectors in the field of heavy ion nuclear research have been well established. Due to high sensitivity, improved charge and mass resolution, easy processing and good digesting capacity for spurious lighter radiations, these detectors have offered several newer potentials in studying the interactions of swift heavy ions in 2π as well as in 4π geometries. A brief review of the recent advances in the following areas of heavy ion research has been presented : (a) a 4π -detection of fusion-fission events and evaporated particles from highly excited compound nuclei, (b) heavy ion induced creation of buckminsterfullerene (C_{60}) and other onion-shell fullerenes (C_{120+}) in carbonaceous compounds, (c) realisation of a new range surface 'ADHIR' a classical analogue of Fermi surface and a new 'RIDGING' phenomenon to explain governed particle motion, (d) development and characterisation of special nuclear track micro-filters (NTMF) for environmental, biological, chemical and industrial applications and (e) development of single pore membrane (SPM) for medical diagnosis. The basic principles, experimental techniques, some recent results and the future scope of the above studies are presented and discussed.

A 4π -detection of fusion-fission events and evaporated particles from highly excited compound nuclei

The application of track detectors in the study of heavy ion interaction are quite well recognized¹⁻⁶. The induced fission of energetic heavy ions and associated particle evaporation⁷⁻¹¹ have motivated us to study such phenomenon in detail. While measuring the etchable track lengths of energetic heavy ions in dielectric solids, a large number of fork-like events were observed. In last couple of years, a nuclear track technique has been developed to analyse the measured track data in 4π geometry into fragment masses, kinetic energies, relative velocities, Q -values, asymmetry parameters, opening angles (in laboratory and centre of mass systems) and pre-fission mass and energy of the fissioning nuclei.

In this section, the experimental procedure and the basic approach for the analysis of fusion-fission events is presented in brief. The results for the fission of ^{238}U and ^{209}Bi ions of different energies in CR-39 have been presented and some important findings on particle evaporation and future scope of this work have been discussed.

Fig. 1. A line diagram of an event indicating various projected and real parameters.

Diagrams and formulae :

Fig. 1 shows the real and projected line diagram of an event. The heavy ion enters the detector surface ('klmn' which is also the observation plane) at a point E making an angle $O'EO (= \alpha)$. After traversing a distance $EO (= L_{pf})$ it undergoes scission at the point O and the fission fragments A and B are ejected in the forward direction and stop at points A and B. The lengths $OA (= L_A)$ and $OB (= L_B)$ represent the ranges of fragments A and B. The opening angles are represented by angle $AOT (= \theta_A)$ and angle $BOT (= \theta_B)$ as shown in Fig. 2. The projections of fission event AOB are drawn on observation plane ($klmn$) and reference plane ($pqrs$) and are designated by $A'O'B'$ and $A''O''B''$ respectively. Following projected data are experimentally measured - $EO' (= l_{pf})$, $O'A' (= l_A)$, $O'B' (= l_B)$, $AA'' (= Z_A)$, $BB'' (= Z_B)$, angle $A'O'X (= \Phi_A)$ and angle $B'O'X (= \Phi_B)$. From these data, the angles $AOA'' (= \beta_A)$ and $BOB'' (= \beta_B)$ can be obtained by $\beta_A = \tan^{-1}(Z_A/L_A)$ and $\beta_B = \tan^{-1}(Z_B/L_B)$ and hence real lengths of the prongs L_A and L_B can be derived from $L_A = Z_A/\sin \beta_A$ and $L_B = Z_B/\sin \beta_B$.

To determine θ_A and θ_B we must look at the events more closely. The prongs of the event may be viewed as two vectors from the point of scission which are normally in the plane containing the axis along the direction of the heavy ion. This plane is inclined at an angle α to the sur-

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Fig. 2. A diagram showing the planes containing the prongs of an event and the tilting angles.

face of the detector. When the prongs (vectors) lie in this plane we say that the prongs are not tilted. It so happens at times that the prongs are tilted by an angle δ from the original plane. This is depicted in Fig. 2. To determine the angle, θ_A and θ_B angles of the prongs are to be evaluated. The relations between the measured projected data and the tilting angles δ_A and δ_B are given as

$$\delta_A = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{((l'_A \cos \Phi_A \tan \alpha) - Z_A)}{l'_A \sin \Phi_A \sec \alpha} \right]$$

$$\delta_B = \tan^{-1} \left[\frac{((l'_B \cos \Phi_B \tan \alpha) - Z_B)}{l'_B \sin \Phi_B \sec \alpha} \right]$$

From these and the other projected data the opening angles θ_A and θ_B are determined using the equations,

$$\theta_A = \sin^{-1} (l'_A \sin \Phi_A / l_A \cos \delta_A)$$

$$\text{and } \theta_B = \sin^{-1} (l'_B \sin \Phi_B / l_B \cos \delta_B)$$

Analysis :

The analysis of fork-like events consists of two parts : (i) transformation of measured track parameters into real ones and (ii) evaluation of different kinematical data of the events from real track parameters.

Transformation of coordinates using program TRANSCORD : The measured values of the dimensions of an event are the projected parameters of the event seen with the help of microscope. Fig. 1 shows the real and projected line diagram of an event. For each event l_{pf} , l'_A , l'_B , Φ_A , Φ_B , Z_A , Z_B , were measured. Here l_{pf} is the pre-fission projected track length, l'_A and l'_B are projected track lengths of prong 'A' and 'B', Φ_A and Φ_B are projected angles of prong 'A' and 'B' with the abscissa. Z_A and Z_B are depth of the tips of prong 'A' and 'B' from the reference plane passing through the point of scission. For analysing the individual events following parameters are required : the real pre-fission track length (L_{pf}), the real lengths of the prongs 'A' and 'B' (L_A and L_B) and the real opening angles (θ_A and

θ_B) of prongs 'A' and 'B' with respect to the direction of motion of the heavy ion. To carry out the entire analysis, a program 'TRANSCORD' (transformation of coordinate) has been developed in FORTRAN. This program consists of two subroutines, viz. PXY and ACTCAL, where PXY finds the energy at the pre-fission point from the pre-fission track length and ACTCAL finds the real parameters from the projected parameters as has been discussed.

Computation of kinematical data from the real track parameters using computer program HIFISS : This part of analysis involves the determination of fragment masses and energies, the relative velocities, Q -values, the asymmetry parameters and the angle between two fragments in the centre of mass system. To evaluate the fragment masses from the measured track data, we take the help of the mass dependent range-velocity calibration coefficients and a 'BINARY SEARCH' ¹² algorithm based on momentum conservation. The procedure of 'BINARY SEARCH' is applied usually for a data structure which has already been created where each node in the 'BINARY TREE' ¹³ is already present but in this case we have developed the algorithm in a way that the generation of next node to be searched is done in the previous step. A dynamic mode of 'BINARY SEARCH' is applied in the present analysis. For any event, if in two consecutive searches the same mass is being repeatedly found and the momentum is not conserved then the event is said to have not passed through the analysis and the program discards such events.

The Q -value of the reaction is the difference of energy in MeV between ETOT and ELAB. Here ETOT is the total kinetic energy of the fragments 'A' and 'B' and ELAB is the energy of the projectile before fission. The relative velocities and the asymmetry parameters of the fission fragments were determined by usual formulations. Similarly the angle between the two fragments in the centre of mass has also been determined. To carry out the entire analysis we have developed the program HIFISS (heavy ion fission) with systematic SUBROUTINES to carry out different purposes in FORTRAN.

Experimental :

Heavy ion irradiation : CR-39 detectors were exposed to well collimated beam of ^{238}U and ^{209}Bi upto the energy of 16.7 MeV/u (MeV per nucleon). The irradiations were done at angles of 30° and 45° to the surface and optimum fluence of 10^4 – 10^5 cm^{-2} was used. All irradiations were done at XO port of UNILAC, GSI, Darmstadt.

Chemical etching and measurement : After irradiations, the CR-39 detectors were etched in 6 N NaOH at 55° for a period of 2–6 h, depending upon the ion energy. Etched samples were mounted on a special specimen holder and scanned under an optical microscope for fork-like events

at a magnification of 150X. The projected track parameters of these events were measured at higher magnification (600X) with the help of a goniometer and a micrometer placed inside the eyepiece and Heidenhain depth measuring device. The number of incident ions were obtained by measuring the track density at several points selected randomly all over the surface. An accuracy of $\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$ in track length and $\pm 2^\circ$ in angles was achieved. More than 400 events for the fission of ^{238}U and nearly 300 events for ^{209}Bi have been measured and analysed in this work.

Analysis of the measured data :

The measured track data are analysed in terms of partial and total induced fission cross-section and eventwise conversion of track lengths and opening angle data into fragment masses, energies, relative velocities, Q -values, asymmetry parameters, and folding angles. The details of the analysing programs TRANSCORD and HIFISS are described elsewhere¹⁰.

Induced fission cross-section : The cross-sections of induced fission of ^{238}U and ^{209}Bi in CR-39 have been obtained as a function of energy using effective detector thickness, number of analysed events and measured fluence of the incident ions. Table 1 lists the partial fission cross-section for ^{238}U and ^{209}Bi in CR-39. The partial cross-sections are obtained for ion energies of 14.2, 11.8, 9.4 and 7.0 McV/u at which the excitation function indicates the presence of resonance peaks⁹.

TABLE 1—PARTIAL FISSION CROSS-SECTION OF ^{238}U AND ^{209}Bi IN CR-39

Ion	Energy MeV/u	Number of events*	Effective detector thickness	Cross-section mb
^{238}U	14.2 ± 0.7	50	16.6	150 ± 20
	11.8 ± 1.1	145	25.0	550 ± 40
	9.4 ± 0.8	70	16.6	400 ± 20
	7.0 ± 1.00	60	19.5	300 ± 20
			Total	
^{209}Bi	11.8 ± 1.0	89	18.6	280 ± 20
	9.4 ± 0.9	77	17.1	490 ± 40
	7.0 ± 1.1	45	19.2	260 ± 20
		Total		1030 ± 50

*Only those events which correspond to resonance peaks.

Analysis of fission events : As stated earlier, our analysing program HIFISS converts track length and opening angle data of individual events into fragment masses, energies, relative velocities, Q -values, asymmetric parameters and folding angles. The mean values of these parameters for 410 events of ^{238}U and 285 events of ^{209}Bi are given in the Table 2.

Analysis of evaporated particles : Nearly 5% of the fork-like fission events show a small track at the point of

bifurcation. These tracks are attributed to the evaporation

TABLE 2—MOST PROBABLE VALUES OF THE ANALYSED PARAMETERS OF ^{238}U AND ^{209}Bi IN CR-39 DETECTORS

Sl no.	Parameter	^{238}U in CR-39	^{209}Bi in CR-39
1.	No. of events	410	285
2.	Pre-fission mass (amu)	252 ± 10	232 ± 10
3.	Q -value (MeV)	+ 150	+ 20
4.	Relative velocity (cm/ns)	2.7 ± 0.3	2.4 ± 0.2
5.	Asymmetry parameter	0 – 0.3	0 – 0.3
6.	Threshold energy for fusion-fission (MeV/u)	5.0	5.0
7.	Particle evaporation (%)	6	–

of the charged particles such as α -particles or other lighter ions from the highly excited projectile nuclei. In order to evaluate the isotropic emission of the evaporated particles, we have tried to determine the direction of the particle from the measured data. A method has been developed and employed for analysis of evaporated particles¹¹.

Error analysis :

Each value of the various parameters determined in the entire analysis has its own significance and hence the effect of the measurement inaccuracies is very important. To quantify this effect, we have changed the measured projected track lengths by $\pm 1.2 \mu\text{m}$, opening angles by $\pm 2^\circ$ and depth of the track tip by $\pm 2 \mu\text{m}$ both individually and collectively. Such changed data when analysed by program TRANSCORD, gave a maximum variation of $\pm 2.3 \mu\text{m}$ in L_A and L_B , $\pm 1.4^\circ$ in θ_A and θ_B and $\pm 4^\circ$ in bending angles δ_A and δ_B . The real track parameters with the above variations when fed into analysing program HIFISS an estimated error of ± 10 amu in total mass, ± 50 MeV in Q -values and ± 0.2 cm/ns in relative velocity was found.

Results and discussion :

Nearly 90% of the measured events are characterised as fission events. Table 2 contains most probable values of certain analysed parameters for fission of ^{238}U and ^{209}Bi in CR-39. These data indicate that the projectile nuclei undergo fission after incomplete or complete fusion. In most cases the two prongs are attributed to fission fragments from their relative velocity, Q -value and mass data.

Although pre-fission mass (252 ± 10) amu supports compound nucleus formation between ^{238}U and ^{12}C or ^{16}O nuclei of CR-39, the corresponding mass (232 ± 10) amu for ^{209}Bi seems to be higher than the fused mass of the projectile with carbon or oxygen nuclei. Under the light of the fact that no such fork-like event has been observed be-

Fig 3 A distribution of total mass, Q -value and relative velocity for fission fragments of ^{238}U in CR-39

Fig 4 A histogram showing distribution of total mass, Q -value and relative velocity for fission fragments of ^{209}Bi in CR-39

low fusion barrier (~ 5 MeV/u) of the projectiles with H, C and O, one may conclude that the fission has occurred only after fusion. With the analysis of more such events for ^{209}Bi one expects to improve the data by minimising statistical fluctuations. Figs. 3-4 show distribution plots of total mass, Q -value and relative velocity of ^{238}U and ^{209}Bi fragments in CR-39 respectively. A fragment mass-yield distribution curve for ^{238}U fission in CR-39 is shown in Fig 5. The masses of median light and median heavy fragments are 115 and 137 respectively. Figs. 6 and 7 show photomicrographs of two events of ^{238}U fission in CR-39 which are associated with single and double particle evaporation respectively.

Fig 5 A plot showing the mass-yield distribution for ^{238}U fission in CR-39

Fig 6 A photomicrograph of an event showing ^{238}U fission in CR 39 and a single evaporate particle at the point of bifurcation

Fig 7 A photomicrograph of a rare event showing ^{238}U fission in CR 39 and two evaporated particles

In order to determine whether the third track is originated from ternary fission or as an evaporated particle from the excited pre-fission nuclei, the angular distribution with reference to projectile direction has been obtained. For this we have measured 16 events for ^{238}U in CR-39 having third track at the point of bifurcation. The track data were analysed by the method explained above. Table 3 lists the relevant data for all the 16 events. It has been observed that 4 particles are emitted in the backward direction. The work is in progress to measure and analyse more events with third track to obtain improved angular distribution in order to distinguish between ternary fission and evaporated residue. The work on identification of emitted particles from track data is also in progress. Experimental evidence for compound nucleus formation¹⁴ and evaporation of neutrons¹⁵ in the reaction of ^{238}U with lighter nuclei have been

reported using active detectors. Further, the evaporation of lighter particles from highly excited compound nucleus has also been predicted¹⁶ but no experimental evidence was provided.

TABLE 3—MEASURED PARAMETERS FOR EVAPORATED PARTICLES FROM EXCITED COMPOUND NUCLEI FORMED BY THE INTERACTION OF ²³⁸U WITH THE MATRIX ATOMS OF CR-39 DETECTOR. THE QUADRANT (Q_d) AND DIRECTION (FORWARD/BACKWARD) OF THIRD TRACK ARE ALSO INDICATED

Sl. no	l_p μm	Z_p μm	L_p μm	E_{pf} MeV/u	θ_p	ϕ_p	δ_p	Q_d	Direction (F/B)
1.	4.48	0	4.48	11.4	245	25	0	III	F
2.	4.48	0	4.48	13.1	250	20	0	III	F
3.	29.12	42.36	51.40	13.5	280	10	83.2	IV	F
4.	6.72	5.3	8.5	11.4	270	0	90.0	III/IV	F
5.	13.44	15.9	20.8	15.2	270	0	90.0	III/IV	F
6.	4.48	7.05	8.4	14.5	115	25	75.0	II	F
7.	7.84	4.93	9.2	15.4	210	60	35.9	III	F
8.	8.96	-7.77	11.86	6.3	240	30	60.0	III	B
9.	13.44	13.77	19.24	9.8	240	30	66.5	III	F
10.	5.6	10.23	11.66	9.8	300	30	74.7	IV	F
11.	6.72	1.2	6.82	9.6	130	40	15.5	II	F
12.	6.72	-3.53	7.59	12.6	245	25	51.2	III	B
13.	4.48	-3.53	5.7	8.2	120	30	57.6	II	B
14.	6.72	-3.29	8.55	8.6	220	50	45.7	III	B
15.	13.44	15.88	20.8	10.8	105	15	77.6	II	F
16.	17.92	10.6	20.8	9.2	285	15	66.3	IV	F

Conclusion :

An analytical approach based on numerical methods has been developed for the analysis of the two pronged events created in SSNTDs by the energetic heavy ions. This paper is a prelude to the entire work undertaken for the study of fusion-fission of ²³⁸U and ²⁰⁹Bi in different SSNTDs. A detailed analysis of such events as based on the basic physics of the phenomenon is in progress. In this work we have demonstrated that with the help of nuclear track detectors (e.g. CR-39), one may study both the fission of heavy projectiles and detection of evaporated particles from highly excited compound nuclei in 4π -geometry. A number of different projectile-detector systems are under investigation to fully develop this field of study.

Heavy ion induced creation of buckminsterfullerene (C_{60}) and other onion-shell fullerenes (C_{120+}) in carbonaceous compounds

Buckminsterfullerene or the bucky ball (C_{60}) molecule was first discovered by Kroto¹⁷. The discovery of this has sparked off a new line of research in structural and synthetic chemistry, material sciences and superconductivity. The synthesis of this compound has been achieved in high-density/high-temperature carbon plasma with intense laser

beams, direct electron irradiation and also in routine carbon-arc discharges.

Positive ions of many even numbered carbon-clusters including C_{60+} have been detected by mass spectrometry from laser ablated graphite surfaces, in electronic back sputtering from heavy ion irradiated PVDF. Here we concentrate on what emerges from the surface during irradiation rather than what remains. Our method points to a molecular synthesis taking place inside the quasi-cylindrical core of the energetic particle tracks. In light of the fact that benzene and other cyclic and polycyclic compounds can be formed by ion bombardment of methane^{18,19}. An attempt has been made to synthesise fullerene molecules by bombardment of carbonaceous matter with massive and highly energetic charged ions.

Experimental :

Two series of experiments were carried out. In the first, clean pyrolytic graphite was irradiated at 90° by a beam of $13.0 \text{ MeV/u } ^{161}\text{Dy}^{22+}$ ions at a flux of 6.4×10^{12} ions/cm². This irradiation was done at UNILAC, GSI, Darmstadt. In the second experiment, Kapton polyimide foils were irradiated in the Van de Graaf injector of the VICKSI HMI, Berlin. The foils were irradiated with $5 \text{ MeV } ^6\text{Li}^{1+}$ at a flux of 1×10^{15} ions/cm² at specific incident angles to the surface ranging from 0 to 70° . The details of the experiment are given in an earlier paper²⁰.

In the graphite irradiation mean electronic and nuclear energy transfer densities were 2 and $6 \times 10^{-4} \text{ eV/\AA}$ respectively, with values of 3.5 (electronic) and 0.1 eV/\AA (nuclear) for polyimide experiments. These values were obtained by using the PRAL computer code of Biersack²¹. The maximum values of electronic energy transferred per unit path-length were 2200 eV/\AA in graphite and 43 eV/\AA in polyimide, the corresponding nuclear energy transfers per unit length being 30 and 9 eV/\AA respectively. These values clearly indicate that the linear energy transfer (LET) is in every case greater than the minimum required for the production of polyaromatic compounds. Despite large real differences of magnitude in the two basic experiments – particularly in terms of projectile mass, energy and target properties – the overall parameters were in fact also chosen so that the familiar generalised energy values were comparable. Detection and analysis were done through chromatography. This was done by refluxing irradiated samples in 2 ml toluene for a week in 10 ml Erlenmeyer flasks equipped with reflux condensers. Liquid samples (*ca.* $200 \mu\text{l}$) were drawn into a syringe through a $0.45 \mu\text{m}$ filter. $20 \mu\text{l}$ aliquots were injected onto a $250 \times 4.6 \text{ mm}$ SS column packed with Intertsill ODS $5 \mu 100 \text{ \AA}$ and eluted with $60\% \text{ CH}_2\text{Cl}_2 + 40\% \text{ MeOH}$ (v/v). The detection wavelength was set at 240 nm . Toluene showed heavy tailing under these

Fig. 8. Chromatographic detector responses for toluene extracts from graphite irradiated with 2.1 GeV ^{161}Dy ions. Shown for comparison are unirradiated graphite, the pure eluent and a calibration solution of strength 5×10^{-8} mol/l.

conditions so that only semi-quantitative conclusions were possible. Irradiated polyimide displayed a relatively weak signal at the C_{60} position. Conversely, the C_{60} signal for irradiated graphite was clear and unambiguous (Fig. 8). Toluene blanks, and extracts from unirradiated graphite on the other hand, gave no corresponding signal.

Results and discussion :

Fig. 8 shows chromatographic results of the present study. The detector response with retention time is plotted for : (a) eluent, (b) non-irradiated graphite, (c) irradiated graphite and (d) calibration solution of C_{60} molecules with a strength of 5×10^{-8} mol/l.

The extract from irradiated graphite gave a small peak at 8.1 ms position with average area being 3440 counts after background subtraction. By comparing this with calibration peak (13411 ± 1000 counts), the concentration of C_{60} in irradiated graphite was determined as 1.3×10^{-8} mol/l. This corresponds to 1.5×10^{13} molecules of C_{60} or a production efficiency of at least 2.3 C_{60} molecules per incident ion of 13.0 MeV/u ^{161}Dy . Small angle neutron scattering experiments have revealed that large (≈ 50 nm) irregular and onion-shell type carbon clusters (C_{120+}) are also produced along with the trails of heavy ions in graphite. More work is required to reveal the detailed nature of these clusters.

Conclusion :

The present study has demonstrated that fullerenes may be created in carbon rich matrix (viz. graphite) by heavy ion bombardment. It is worthwhile to pursue further work to understand some basic questions like : (a) how does the rate of fullerene synthesis depend on projectile and target species, target temperature, particle flux etc.? and (b) whether the extraction efficiency in chromatography can be improved ? The use of other complementary techniques, such as high resolution TEM analytical work and applications of chromatography, coupled with the polymer foil stack technique will be important in vital studies of transverse track structure and in proper determinations of fullerene production efficiency with depth.

Angular dependence of heavy ion range (ADHIR) of energetic ^{209}Bi in mica and polycarbonate

In an effort to understand the effect of the crystal structure on the path of a highly energetic charged particle we had earlier bombarded muscovite mica at three different angles with a beam of 1.65 GeV ^{132}Xe ions²². Mica being an anisotropic material exhibits such phenomenon as channelling, quasi-channelling and blocking. It has been observed through optical microscope during our experiment that the ranges vary systematically with the angle of incidence. These anomalous ranges have been ascribed to repeated and curved refracted orbits in the molecular layers. The detailed angular influence on these orbits in turn produced a strong 'non-linear' effect on the stopping-power. This has introduced new concept of 'ridging' and 'bridging' of particle trajectories²³.

In the present work we have further extended the earlier investigation on muscovite mica by bombarding it at five different angles from 15 to 75° with ^{209}Bi ions at an energy of 2.72 GeV. An isotropic dielectric detector Bayer polycarbonate was also irradiated at the same angles with ions of the same energy. The variation of range with the angle of incidence gives an indication of the amount of 'ridging' or 'bridging' that is involved.

Experimental :

Two types of detectors were used in this work : (a) isotropic crystalline detector muscovite mica (chemical formula $\text{KAl}_2(\text{OH})_2\text{Si}_3\text{AlO}_{10}$ with a density of 2.81 g/ml) and (b) an isotropic plastic detector which is a polycarbonate (chemical formula $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ and a density of 1.20 g/ml). This polycarbonate is manufactured by Bayer AG (Germany).

The two detectors were irradiated with 2.72 GeV ^{209}Bi ions at UNILAC, GSI, Darmstadt. The irradiations were done at a flux of 10^5 cm^{-2} at precisely controlled irradiation

tion angles of 15, 30, 45, 60 and 75° to the detector surface. The detectors were then etched under different optimum conditions in order to obtain the maximum etchable track lengths. Muscovite mica was etched in 20% HF at 60° for a period of 30 min in order to develop the tracks till the end of their trajectories. Polycarbonate was etched in 6 N NaOH at 60° for a period of 90 min. The detectors were then taken out, washed, dried and then observed under the microscope and the track parameters were measured. The measurements were done with a Leitz (Laborlux D) microscope at a magnification of 1875X. The total numbers of tracks measured in each detector varied from 93 to 193 tracks per detector. The maximum etchable track lengths were obtained from the relation given by Dwivedi and Mukherji²⁴. The standard deviations obtained ranged from 1.5 to 3.5 μm .

Results and discussion :

Table 4 lists the ranges obtained at different angles of incidence for muscovite mica. The number of tracks measured on each detector as well as the theoretical values obtained from the different computer codes – RANGE²⁵, TRIM²⁶ and BENTON's program²⁷. It is found that there is a gradual increase in range from 15 to 75° as each layer crossed gradually adds up to the range. However, the mean ranges obtained experimentally were found to differ appreciably from the theoretical values. The experimental ranges obtained between 45–75° were found to agree quite well with the theoretical values.

TABLE 4—EXPERIMENTAL RANGES OF 2.72 GeV ²⁰⁹B₁ IONS IN MICA INCIDENT AT FIVE DIFFERENT ANGLES

Sample no.	Angle (degree)	No. of tracks measured	Experimental mean range (μm)
MBi-1	15	93	89.0 \pm 1.5
MBi-2	30	193	92.5 \pm 1.5
MBi-3	45	178	95.6 \pm 1.8
MBi-4	60	191	99.7 \pm 2.0
MBi-5	75	189	103.1 \pm 2.2

Theoretical ranges : (a) RANGE : 98.2 μm , (b) TRIM : 102.5 μm and (c) BENTON : 99.3 μm .

TABLE 5—EXPERIMENTAL RANGES OF 2.72 GeV ²⁰⁹B₁ IONS IN POLYCARBONATE INCIDENT AT FIVE DIFFERENT ANGLES

Sample no	Angle (degree)	No. of tracks measured	Experimental mean range (μm)
PC-15	15	154	173.6 \pm 1.7
PC-30	30	154	172.9 \pm 1.7
PC-45	45	164	172.6 \pm 2.0
PC-60	60	154	171.5 \pm 2.6
PC-75	75	167	174.2 \pm 3.5

Theoretical ranges : (a) RANGE : 181.0 μm , (b) TRIM : 195.0 μm and (c) BENTON : 175.7 μm .

Table 5 lists the ranges (experimental and theoretical), number of tracks and the angle of incidence obtained for the polycarbonate detector. The ranges are found to agree with each other within the limits of experimental errors. Another factor to be noted is that the range values at different angles of incidence do not differ appreciably with each other. This shows that the dependence of range with the angle of incidence is minimal. The steering and gradual addition of range to the total range is negligible in the case of polycarbonate detector. Taking the range value at 45° angle of incidence to be representative value, the theoretical values obtained from Benton's program²⁷ are found to agree better with the experimental values than the other theoretical values.

Development and characterisation of special nuclear track micro-filters (NTMF) for diverse applications

One of the premier applications of nuclear track filters has been in the production of nuclear track microfilters or NTMFs which have been utilised in a wide range of fields^{28–30}. Ion track filters are unique due to the fact that they are defined by very few parameters, viz. the track length, track diameter and the areal density of the ion tracks. These parameters can be varied in an easily controllable way over several orders of magnitude. In this way they offer distinct advantages over conventional filters which are ruled by several mutually interdependent processing parameters²⁹.

The choice of detector material for preparing micro-filters is based on their response to etching in terms of the homogeneity and smoothness of pore walls after etching. The mechanical strength, chemical and radiation resistance of the detector material also plays a great role^{31–36}. In this particular work we have used Makrofol-N a polycarbonate. The Makrofol-N pieces were irradiated with ¹⁶¹Dy ions with an energy of 13.0 MeV/u. Five microfilters with different filter specifications controlled by varying etching conditions were prepared. The performance of these microfilters has been assessed for their possible applications in the following process : (a) determination of the concentration of liquid solutions and (b) determination of the viscosity of a liquid solution.

The special features of NTMF :

The pore shape and size is dependent on the nature of the bombarding ion (mass, charge and energy), the irradiation geometry and etching parameters like relative magnitude of bulk and track etch rates. By regulating the etching conditions, one may develop well-defined pores of desired size and shape. Cylindrical channels are developed when track etch rate (V_T) is very high compared to bulk etch rate (V_G), while tapered holes are produced by careful adjust-

ment of etching conditions so that the V_T/V_G ratio is not too high.

One advantage of microfilters over conventional filters is that certain parameters may be controlled while producing a Nuclear Track Microfilter of a given dielectric foil. These are : (a) pore density, (b) outer and inner diameter of the pores, (c) length of the pore, (d) tapering angle and (e) porosity. One of the important criterion in the preparation of filters is their porosity. The term porosity is defined as the ratio of the total areas covered by the pores to the total area of the filter. For tapered filter pores, the apparent porosity is due to the cross-sectional area of the pores at the surface. While the effective porosity is related to the inner cross-sectional area of the pores. If the outer and inner diameters are D and d and the pore density N_p then

$$P_{app} (\%) = CN_p \cdot \pi D^2$$

and

$$P_{eff} (\%) = CN_p \cdot \pi d^2$$

where, C is a constant which is equal to 25×10^{-8} , N_p the pore density (cm^{-2}) and the diameters D and d are in μm .

Experimental :

Makrofol-N (a trade name of bisphenol-A-polycarbonate, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$, Bayer AG, FRG) was used to prepare filters in the present experiment. Circular pieces (47 mm) of the material were exposed to a well-collimated beam of ^{161}Dy after mounting on a special sample holder. The irradiations were done at GSI, UNILAC (Germany) at an incident angle of 90° with flux of 5×10^6 ions/ cm^2 at an energy of 13.0 MeV/ u . The foils were etched in 3 N NaOH at 55° for different periods so that micropores were developed with outer pore diameters 0.6, 1.2, 1.8, 2.4 and 3.6 μm . After washing and drying the pore diameters were measured with an optical microscope (Leitz, Laborlux D). Fig. 9 shows a SEM (JFC-1100-(JEOL)) microphotograph of a portion of the filter. The measurements were done at a

Fig. 9. A SEM photomicrograph of a portion of nuclear track microfilter.

magnification of 1250X using a 100X water immersion objective while the pore density was determined using a graticule of 1.0 cm^2 divided in to 100×100 grids.

Applications of nuclear track micro-filters :

The five filters have been characterised according to different parameters as mentioned elsewhere³⁵. The performance of these filters was assessed in terms of their rate of filtration of prefiltered distilled water whereupon it was found that the rate of filtration depended on the nature of the surface. The rate of filtration was found to be 2 or 3 times higher when the rough surface is used for filtration than the smooth surface. The various applications of the filters have been tested using the smooth surface for filtration rather than the rough surface.

Determination of the concentration of liquid solutions :

The unknown concentration of ethylene glycol and glycerine was determined by measuring the rate of filtration of the various solutions through different microfilters. Five different concentrations of glycerine (viz. 5, 10, 15, 20 and 25%) and ethylene glycol (viz. 20, 30, 40, 50 and 60%) were prepared. Out of these one solution each, i.e. 40% ethylene glycol and 15% glycerine was taken to be unknown. A known volume of these solutions was filtered through three different microfilters (MF-3, MF-4 and MF-5) with and without suction. The rates of filtration of different solutions of ethylene glycol and glycerine were determined. It is observed that the filtration rate increases with increasing pore diameter. The filtration rate for these solutions varied between 2.7 to 33.3 ml/s with suction and between 0.045 to 0.133 ml/s without suction. Calibration curves for ethylene glycol and glycerine were prepared. From these curves, the unknown concentration of the solutions were determined by measuring their filtration rates. With microfilter MF-3 (pore diameters 1.8 μm) the unknown concentrations of ethylene glycol was found to be 42.5%, whereas values of 38% was determined using the microfilter MF-4. These values are within 6% of the theoretical values.

In the case of glycerine, the concentrations determined by MF-3 and MF-4 were found to be 15.0 and 15.5 respectively. These values are within 4% of the theoretical values. Similar studies were carried out with microfilter MF-5 but without any suction. For microfilters MF-3 and MF-4 the calibration curves as a function of the rate of filtration (R_f) with suction and glycerine solution concentrations are shown in Fig. 10. From the values of filtration rate 4.7 and 16.7 ml/s the unknown concentrations of glycerine were found to be 15.0 and 15.5%, which show a good agreement with the theoretical values. These results indicate that NTMFs can be effectively used in the determination of solution concentrations.

Fig. 10. Calibration curves showing the variation of filtration rate (R_f) of different solutions of glycerine through MF-3 and MF-4 microfilters (pore diameters : 1.8 and 2.4 μm) as a function of their concentrations using suction mode.

Determination of the viscosity of liquid solutions : It has been observed³⁷ that under identical filtration conditions the viscosity of a liquid is directly proportional to its filtration rate. Keeping this in mind we have used the microfilters in the determination of the viscosity of n-butanol. For this experiment the filtration time for equal volumes of isobutanol, ethylene glycol, diethyl ether and n-butanol were measured with MF-3. The data are listed in Table 6 along with their viscosity values as stated in literature³⁸. A calibration curve is drawn between the filtration rate (ml/s) and viscosity (cp) for isobutanol, ethylene glycol and diethyl ether. The filtration rate for n-butanol is found to be 8.3 ml/s which corresponds to a viscosity of 3.0 cp from the calibration curve. The value given for n-butanol is 2.95 cp at 20°. A good agreement between the experimental and theoretical values of viscosity is indicative of a potential application of these microfilters to be used as a simple device for the determination of the viscosity of a liquid.

TABLE 6—EXPERIMENTAL VALUES OF THE FILTRATION RATE OF DIFFERENT SOLVENTS USING MICRO-FILTER MF-3 ALONG WITH THEIR VISCOSITY

Solvent	Viscosity cp	Filtration rate (R_f) ml/s
Isobutanol	4.21	5.9
Ethylenglycol	19.90	1.5
Diethyl ether	0.22	20.0
n-Butanol	3.00 ^a	8.3
	2.95 ^b	

^aFrom present work. ^bFrom literature (Ref. 38).

Conclusion :

The studies performed above show the applicability of these filters in determination of the concentration and viscosity of liquids. A calibration curve produced over a wider range would enhance the utility of the technique. These NTMFs may also be used in a variety of other applications in many diverse fields. (i) *Environmental sciences* : (a) Collection and size fractionation of aerosols, (b) filtration of natural water to produce bacteria-free pure drinking water and (c) separation of radioactive gases like radon and thoron. (ii) *Chemical sciences* : (a) Purification of liquids, (b) separation of gas/liquid, liquid/liquid and gas/liquid/solid phases, (c) purification of helium, (d) as ion-selective membranes after modification and (e) in liquid and gas chromatography. (iii) *Industrial processes* : (a) Desalination of sea water by reverse osmosis and (b) removal of radioactivity from prime-loop water of nuclear power plant. (iv) *Biomedical sciences* : (a) In cancer therapy and (b) as transdermal delivery system (TDS) to supply controlled doses of drugs. (v) *Material sciences* : (a) In production of super insulators, (b) in production of random field-emitter for their applications as energy saving cold cathodes in vacuum electronics devices, (c) in production of heterojunctions and (d) in production of hollow metallic microtubes.

Development of single-pore membranes for medical diagnosis

An important aspect in medical diagnostics is the counting, sizing and separation of individual living cells, and it is in this field that single-pore membranes find their utmost utility. As single pores can be used to count, size and measure the electrokinetic mobility of sub-micron size particles it extends the scope of flow cytometry into the sub-microscopic range. This technique has been applied to measure the internal cell parameters, i.e. the deformability of individual red blood cells by using a single pore with about 4 μm diameter³⁹.

Experimental :

The single-pore membranes were prepared by exposing polymeric films to energetic heavy ions in such a way that only one ion goes across the film in each frame. For this the film was continuously moved through a motor and the heavy ion beam was chopped through an electronic chopper to allow only one ion to impinge on the film at a time. After each exposure the film was advanced by 19 mm. Makrofol-E (a polycarbonate) films are extensively used for making single-pore membranes. Exposed films were etched in NaOH at 40° for 250–300 min to develop single pores to 4–5 μm in diameter. Each pore was accurately measured with the help of an optical microscope at high magnification.

Applications :

In order to understand the applications of single-pore membranes to the deformability of red blood cells (RBC), a review of the physiology of RBC is essential. RBCs are oblate disk (doughnut) shaped particles with a diameter of about 7.5 μm and a thickness range of 1–2 μm . A healthy RBC is extremely flexible and it can easily squeeze through the finer capillaries (3–5 μm) of the human body. However, many diseases of heart and circulatory system have been traced recently to an insufficient deformability of the RBCs. Extensive research work is now involved in studying the flow behaviour of blood in the capillary network. Using single-pore membranes, a special unit⁴⁰ has been developed to study the plasticity of RBCs. This cell counter unit measures the passage time of each blood cell. It has been observed that the infected cells lose their flexibility and become more plastic than the normal cells, hence they take longer passage time than the normal cells. The single-pore membranes have been used in studying several internal cell parameters in medical diagnostics.

Apart from the above applications, the single-pore membranes are also used in vacuum technology and mass spectrometry as 'gas-inlet leaks'⁴¹. The single-pore membranes are being exploited in developing 'weak links' to study superconductive Josephson effect⁴².

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References

1. R. HAAG, G. FIEDLER, R. ULBRICH, G. BREITBACH and P. A. GOTTSCHALK, *Z. Phys A: Atoms Nuclei*, 1984, **316**, 183.
2. K. K. DWIVEDI, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1991, **19**, 71.
3. P. B. PRICE, *Ann Rev Nucl Part Sci.*, 1989, **39**, 19.
4. R. BONETTI, C. CHIESA, A. GUGLIEMETTI, C. MIGLIORINO, A. CESANA and M. TERRANI, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1991, **19**, 579.
5. P. A. GOTTSCHALK, G. GRAWERT, P. VATER and R. BRANDT, *Phys. Rev.*, 1983, **C27**, 2703.
6. R. BRANDT, P. A. GOTTSCHALK and P. VATER, *Nucl Instrum Meth.*, 1980, **173**, 111.
7. M. DEBEAUVAIS, J. RALAROSY, J. TRIPIER and S. JOKIC in 'Proc. of the 11th. Int. Conf. on SSNTD', eds. P. H. FOWLER and V. M. CLAPHAM, Pergamon, New York, 1982, p. 763.
8. M. DEBEAUVAIS and J. RALAROSY, *Nucleus*, 1983, **20**, 99.
9. K. K. DWIVEDI and G. FIEDLER, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1988, **15**, 353.
10. J. RAJU and K. K. DWIVEDI, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1993, **22**, 609.
11. K. K. DWIVEDI, J. RAJU, P. VATER and R. BRANDT, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1993, **22**, 577.
12. H. HOROWITZ and S. SAHNI, "Fundamentals of Data Structures in Pascal", Galgotia Publications, New Delhi, 1983.
13. J. W. COOPER, "Introduction to Pascal for Scientist", Wiley-Intersciences, New York, 1975.
14. J. TOKE, R. BOCK, GUANG-XI DAI, A. GOBBI, S. GRALLA, K. D. HILDERBRAND, J. KUZMINSKI, W. F. J. MULLER, A. OLMI and W. REISDORF, *Phys Lett.*, 1984, **142B**, 258.
15. T. SIKKELAND, J. MALY and D. F. LEBECK, *Phys Rev.*, 1968, **169**, 1000.
16. R. BOCK, H. EMLING and K. D. HILDERBRAND, *Interdisciplinary Sci Rev.*, 1984, **9**, 305.
17. H. W. KROTO, J. R. HEATH, S. C. O'BRIEN, R. F. CURL and R. E. SMALLEY, *Nature*, 1985, **318**, 162.
18. R. I. KAISER, R. M. MAHFOUZ and K. ROSSLER, *Nucl Instr Meth.*, 1992, **B65**, 468.
19. R. I. KAISER, J. LAUTERWAIN, P. MÜLLER and K. ROSSLER, *Nucl Instr Meth.*, 1992, **B65**, 463.
20. L. T. CHADDERTON, D. W. FINK, H. MOCKEL, K. K. DWIVEDI and A. HAMMOUDI, *Rad. Eff Defects Solids*, 1993, **127**, 163.
21. J. P. BIRSACK, *Z. Physik.*, 1982, **A315**, 95.
22. S. GHOSH, A. SAXENA and K. K. DWIVEDI, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1988, **15**, 349.
23. L. T. CHADDERTON, S. GHOSH, A. SAXENA, K. K. DWIVEDI, J. P. BIRSACK and D. W. FINK, *Nucl. Instrum Meth.*, 1990, **B46**, 46.
24. K. K. DWIVEDI and S. MUKHERJI, *Nucl Instrum Meth.*, 1979, **161**, 317.
25. K. K. DWIVEDI, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1988, **15**, 345.
26. J. P. BIRSACK and L. G. HAGGMARK, *Nucl Instrum Meth.*, 1980, **174**, 257.
27. R. P. HENKE and E. V. BENTON, *USNRDL TR-67-122* (1968).
28. S. SEAL, *Cancer*, 1964, **1**, 637.
29. R. SPOHR, "Ion Tracks and Microtechnology—Principles and Applications", Vieweg Verlag, Braunschweig, 1990.
30. R. W. DEBLOIS and C. P. BEAN, *Rev Sci Instrum*, 1970, **41**, 909.
31. Y. KOMAKI, *Nucl Tracks*, 1979, **3**, 33.
32. P. VATER, G. TRESS, R. BRANDT, B. GENSWURGER and R. SPOHR, *Nucl Instrum Meth.*, 1980, **173**, 205.
33. M. BERNDT, J. KRALUSE, G. SIEGMON and W. ENGE, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1986, **12**, 985.
34. ZHU TIAN-CHENG, R. BRANDT, P. VATER and J. VETTER, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1988, **15**, 771.
35. M. DFY, J. RAJU, S. GHOSH and K. K. DWIVEDI, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1992, **22**, 907.
36. S. HEISE, K. K. DWIVEDI, P. VATER, R. BRANDT and C. DANKMEYER, *Nucl Tracks Radiat Meas.*, 1993, **22**, 909.
37. S. L. GLO, M. GANZ, M. FUEST, P. VATER and R. BRANDT, *Isotopenpraxis*, 1990, **26**, 272.
38. "CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", 55th. ed., CRC Press, Cleveland, 1974-75, F-50 to F-55.
39. H. G. ROGGENKAMP, H. KIESEWETTER, R. SPOHR, U. DAUER and L. C. BUSCH, *Biomedizinische Technik*, 1981, **26**, 167.
40. H. G. ROGGENKAMP, H. KIESEWETTER, T. SCHMEINH and H. G. HOLLWEG, *Biomedizinische Technik*, 1982, **27**, 162.
41. B. E. FISCHER and R. SPOHR, *Rev Mod Phys.*, 1983, **55**, 907.
42. J. P. PEKOLA, J. C. DAVIS, YU-QIN ZHU, R. N. R. SPOHR, P. B. PRICE and R. E. PACKARD, *J Low Temp Phys.*, 1987, **67**, 47.